

A note on SDD invariants of clump graphs with Girth size at most three

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Abstract: The symmetric division deg invariant is one of the 200 discrete Adriatic indices introduced several years ago. This SDD invariant has been already proved a valuable invariant in the QSAR(Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship) and QSPR(Quantitative Structure Property Relationship) studies. In this article, we present on exact values of SDD invariants of inorganic Clump graphs with girth size at most three.

Key words: Degree, Zagreb invariant, symmetric division deg invariant

1. Introduction

All the inorganic graphs, unless otherwise specified, are finite, undirected, connected, and simple. Molecular descriptors, being numerical functions of molecular structure, play a prominent role in mathematical chemistry and are used in QSAR and QSPR studies [8] that relate biological or chemical properties of molecules to specific molecular descriptors [3]. Many molecular descriptors are defined as functions of the structure of the underlying molecular graph, such as the Wiener invariant [10], the Zagreb invariant [5] and Balaban invariants [2]. D.Vukicevic et al. proved that many of these descriptors are defined as individual bond contributions. Among the 200 discrete Adriatic invariants studied in [11], whose predictive properties were evaluated against the benchmark datasets of the International Academy of Mathematical Chemistry [6], 20 invariants were selected as significant predictors of physiochemical properties. The Symmetric division deg index is one of the discrete Adriatic indices which is a good predictor of total surface area for polychlorobiphenyls and some of the results on symmetric division deg index are also found in [3]. In [1], obtained an expression to introduce the symmetric division deg invariant of some derived graphs and its complements and also [7] introduce a splice graph and its operations like edge subdivision, edge neighborhood subdivision, vertex neighborhood subdivision, vertex subdivision graphs, In this note we concentrated on inorganic clump graphs with a girth size of at most three. The girth of a graph is the length of the shortest cycle contained in a graph and is denoted by $[g]$. Since a tree has no cycles, we define its girth as infinity. It is shown that a complete graph with $n-1$ regular graphs shares many properties with a girth of size almost three.

2. Some clump graphs

From a chemical point of view, graphs with large number of edges may be considered as representations of inorganic clumps, called clump graphs. Bearing this in mind, we consider have the graphs obtained from the complete graphs K_s by removing some of its edges. In this section, we establish SDD invariant of following four types of clump graphs.

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Type I Let $e_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, t, 1 \leq t \leq s - 2$ be distinct edges of the complete graphs $K_s, s \geq 3$ all being incident to a single vertex. The graph $Ka_s(t)$ is obtained by deleting $e_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, t$ from K_s . Note that $Ka_s(0) \cong K_s$.

Type II Let $e'_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, t, 1 \leq t \leq \lfloor \frac{s}{2} \rfloor$ be independent edges of the complete graph $Kb_s(t)$ is obtained by deleting $e'_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, t$ from K_s . Note that $Kb_s(0) \cong K_s$.

Type III Let V_t be a t element subset of the vertex set of $k_s, 2 \leq t \leq s - 1, s \geq 3$. The graph $Kc_s(t)$ is obtained by deleting from K_s all the edges connecting pairs of vertices from V_t . Note that $Kc_s(0) \cong Kc_s(1) \cong K_s$.

Type IV Let $s \geq 3, 3 \geq t \geq s$. The graph $Kd_s(t)$ is obtained by deleting from K_s the edges belonging to a t -membered cycles.

Theorem 2.1. For $[g], s \geq 3$ and $1 \leq t \leq s - 2,$ $SDD(Ka_s(t)) = t(t - 1) + (s - t - 1)(s - t - 2) + \frac{2(s-1)^2+t^2-2t(s-1)}{(s-1)} + t(s - t - 1) \left[\frac{2s^2-6s+5}{(s-2)(s-1)} \right]$.

Proof: One can see that the graph $Ka_s(t)$ has s vertices and $\frac{s(s-1)}{2} - t$ edges. We can partition the edges set of $Ka_s(t)$ as follows;

$$E_1 = \{a_1 a_2 | \lambda_{Ka_s(t)}(a_1) = s - 1 - t, \lambda_{Ka_s(t)}(a_2) = s - 1\}.$$

$$E_2 = \{a_1 a_2 | \lambda_{Ka_s(t)}(a_1) = s - 1, \lambda_{Ka_s(t)}(a_2) = s - 2\}.$$

$$E_3 = \{a_1 a_2 | \lambda_{Ka_s(t)}(a_1) = s - 2, \lambda_{Ka_s(t)}(a_2) = s - 1\}.$$

$$E_4 = \{a_1 a_2 | \lambda_{Ka_s(t)}(a_1) = s - 1, \lambda_{Ka_s(t)}(a_2) = s - 1\}.$$

Clearly $E(Ka_s(t)) = E_1 \cup E_2 \cup E_3 \cup E_4$ and $|E_1| = s - t - 1, |E_2| = \frac{t(t-1)}{2}, |E_3| = t(s - t - 1), |E_4| = \frac{(s-t-1)(s-t-2)}{2}$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} SDD(Ka_s(t)) &= \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{a_1 a_2 \in E_i} \frac{\lambda_{Ka_s(t)}(a_1)^2 + \lambda_{Ka_s(t)}(a_2)^2}{\lambda_{Ka_s(t)}(a_1) \lambda_{Ka_s(t)}(a_2)} \\ &= (s - t - 1) \left[\frac{(s - t - 1)^2 + (s - 1)^2}{(s - t - 1)(s - 1)} \right] + \frac{t(t - 1)}{2} \left[\frac{(s - 2)^2 + (s - 2)^2}{(s - 2)(s - 2)} \right] \\ &+ t(s - t - 1) \left[\frac{(s - 2)^2 + (s - 1)^2}{(s - 2)(s - 1)} \right] + \frac{(s - t - 1)(s - t - 2)}{2} \left[\frac{(s - 1)^2 + (s - 1)^2}{(s - 1)(s - 1)} \right] \\ &= \frac{(s - t - 1)^2 + (s - 1)^2}{(s - 1)} + \frac{t(t - 1)}{2} \left[\frac{2(s - 2)^2}{(s - 2)^2} \right] \\ &+ t(s - t - 1) \left[\frac{(s - 2)^2 + (s - 1)^2}{(s - 2)(s - 1)} \right] + \frac{(s - t - 1)(s - t - 2)}{2} \left[\frac{2(s - 1)^2}{(s - 1)^2} \right] \\ &= t(t - 1) + (s - t - 1)(s - t - 2) + \frac{2(s - 1)^2 + t^2 - 2t(s - 1)}{(s - 1)} \\ &+ t(s - t - 1) \left[\frac{2s^2 - 6s + 5}{(s - 2)(s - 1)} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.2. For $[g], s \geq 3$ and $1 \leq t \leq \lfloor \frac{s}{2} \rfloor,$ $SDD(Kb_s(t)) = 2t(s - 2t) \left[\frac{2s^2-6s+5}{(s-2)(s-1)} \right] + 2t(2t - 1) + (s -$

$$2t)(s - 2t - 1) - 2t.$$

Proof: One can easily check that the number of vertices and number of edges of $Kb_s(t)$ are respectively, s and $\frac{s(s-1)}{2} - t$. We can partition the edges set of $Kb_s(t)$ as follows;

$$E_1 = \{a_1a_2 | \lambda_{Kb_s(t)}(a_1) = s - 2, \lambda_{Kb_s(t)}(a_2) = s - 1\}.$$

$$E_2 = \{a_1a_2 | \lambda_{Kb_s(t)}(a_1) = s - 1, \lambda_{Kb_s(t)}(a_2) = s - 1\}.$$

$$E_3 = \{a_1a_2 | \lambda_{Kb_s(t)}(a_1) = s - 2, \lambda_{Kb_s(t)}(a_2) = s - 2\}.$$

We can observe that $|E_1| = 2t(s - 2t)$, $|E_2| = \frac{(s-2t)(s-2t-1)}{2}$, $|E_3| = \left(\frac{2t(2t-1)}{2}\right) - t$ and $E(Kb_s(t)) = E_1 \cup E_2 \cup E_3$. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} SDD(Kb_s(t)) &= \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{a_1a_2 \in E_i} \frac{\lambda_{Kb_s(t)}(a_1)^2 + \lambda_{Kb_s(t)}(a_2)^2}{\lambda_{Kb_s(t)}(a_1)\lambda_{Kb_s(t)}(a_2)} \\ &= 2t(s - 2t) \left[\frac{(s-2)^2 + (s-1)^2}{(s-2)(s-1)} \right] + \frac{(s-2t)(s-2t-1)}{2} \left[\frac{(s-1)^2 + (s-1)^2}{(s-1)(s-1)} \right] \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{2t(2t-1)}{2} - t \right) \left[\frac{(s-2)^2 + (s-2)^2}{(s-2)(s-2)} \right] \\ &= 2t(s - 2t) \left[\frac{(s-2)^2 + (s-1)^2}{(s-2)(s-1)} \right] + \frac{(s-2t)(s-2t-1)}{2} \left[\frac{2(s-1)^2}{(s-1)^2} \right] \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{2t(2t-1)}{2} - t \right) \left[\frac{2(s-2)^2}{(s-2)^2} \right] \\ &= 2t(s - 2t) \left[\frac{2s^2 - 6s + 5}{(s-2)(s-1)} \right] + 2t(2t-1) + (s-2t)(s-2t-1) - 2t. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.3. For $[g]$, $s \geq 3$ and $2 \leq t \leq s - 1$, $SDD(Kc_s(t)) = (s-t)(s-t-1) + t \left[\frac{(s-t)^2 + (s-1)^2}{(s-1)} \right]$.

Proof: One can see that $|V((Kc_s(t)))| = s$ and $|E((Kc_s(t)))| = \frac{(s-t)(s-t-1)}{2}$. Moreover we can partition the edge set of the graph $Kc_s(t)$ as follows;

$$E_1 = \{a_1a_2 | \lambda_{Kc_s(t)}(a_1) = s - t, \lambda_{Kc_s(t)}(a_2) = s - 1\} \text{ and } |E_1| = (s-t)t \text{ and}$$

$$E_2 = \{a_1a_2 | \lambda_{Kc_s(t)}(a_1) = s - 1, \lambda_{Kc_s(t)}(a_2) = s - 1\} \text{ and } |E_2| = \frac{(s-t)(s-t-1)}{2}. \text{ Hence}$$

$$\begin{aligned} SDD(Kc_s(t)) &= \sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{a_1a_2 \in E_i} \frac{\lambda_{Kc_s(t)}(a_1)^2 + \lambda_{Kc_s(t)}(a_2)^2}{\lambda_{Kc_s(t)}(a_1)\lambda_{Kc_s(t)}(a_2)} \\ &= (s-t)t \left[\frac{(s-t)^2 + (s-1)^2}{(s-t)(s-1)} \right] + \frac{(s-t)(s-t-1)}{2} \left[\frac{(s-1)^2 + (s-1)^2}{(s-1)(s-1)} \right] \\ &= t \left[\frac{(s-t)^2 + (s-1)^2}{(s-1)} \right] + \frac{(s-t)(s-t-1)}{2} \left[\frac{2(s-1)^2}{(s-1)^2} \right] \\ &= (s-t)(s-t-1) + t \left[\frac{(s-t)^2 + (s-1)^2}{(s-1)} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.4. For $[g], s \geq 3$ and $2 \leq t \leq s-1$, $SDD(Kd_s(t)) = t(t-3) + (s-t)(s-t-1) + (st-t^2) \left[\frac{2s^2-8s+10}{(s-3)(s-1)} \right]$.

Proof: Note that $|V(Kd_s(t))| = s$ and $|E((Kd_s(t)))| = \frac{s(s-1)}{2} - t$. Form the structure of the graph $Kd_s(t)$ we have following edge partitions;

$$E_1 = \{a_1 a_2 | \lambda_{Kd_s(t)}(a_1) = s-3, \lambda_{Kd_s(t)}(a_2) = s-3\}.$$

$$E_2 = \{a_1 a_2 | \lambda_{Kd_s(t)}(a_1) = s-3, \lambda_{Kd_s(t)}(a_2) = s-1\}.$$

$$E_3 = \{a_1 a_2 | \lambda_{Kd_s(t)}(a_1) = s-1, \lambda_{Kd_s(t)}(a_2) = s-1\}.$$

$$\text{Moreover, } |E_1| = \frac{t(t-1)}{2} - t, |E_2| = t(s-t), |E_3| = \frac{(s-t)(s-t-1)}{2}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} SDD(Kd_s(t)) &= \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{a_1 a_2 \in E_i} \frac{\lambda_{Kd_s(t)}(a_1)^2 + \lambda_{Kd_s(t)}(a_2)^2}{\lambda_{Kd_s(t)}(a_1) \lambda_{Kd_s(t)}(a_2)} \\ &= \left(\frac{t(t-1)}{2} - t \right) \left[\frac{(s-3)^2 + (s-3)^2}{(s-3)(s-3)} \right] + \left(t(s-t) \right) \left[\frac{(s-3)^2 + (s-1)^2}{(s-3)(s-1)} \right] \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{(s-t)(s-t-1)}{2} \right) \left[\frac{(s-1)^2 + (s-1)^2}{(s-1)(s-1)} \right] \\ &= \left(\frac{t(t-1)}{2} - t \right) \left[\frac{2(s-3)^2}{(s-3)^2} \right] + \left(t(s-t) \right) \left[\frac{(s-3)^2 + (s-1)^2}{(s-3)(s-1)} \right] \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{(s-t)(s-t-1)}{2} \right) \left[\frac{2(s-1)^2}{(s-1)^2} \right] \\ &= \left(\frac{t(t-1)}{2} - t \right) (2) + \left(t(s-t) \right) \left[\frac{(s-3)^2 + (s-1)^2}{(s-3)(s-1)} \right] \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{(s-t)(s-t-1)}{2} \right) (2) \\ &= t(t-1) - 2t + (st-t^2) \left[\frac{(s-3)^2 + (s-1)^2}{(s-3)(s-1)} \right] \\ &\quad + (s-t)(s-t-1) \\ &= t(t-3) + (s-t)(s-t-1) + (st-t^2) \left[\frac{2s^2-8s+10}{(s-3)(s-1)} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

3. Conclusion

In this note we have exhibited the existence of inorganic clump graphs and also evinced the exact values of SDD invariants of graphs with grith size atmost three.

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